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**The Role of the Educational Purposes of Islamic
Worship in Facing the Problems of Modern
Technology among University Youth (Afield
study)**

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Abstract

The study aimed to propose a conceptual framework for activating the educational objectives of Islamic acts of worship among university youth to address the challenges posed by modern technology. It also sought to identify the main obstacles hindering this activation. The study adopted a descriptive methodology and employed a questionnaire as the primary research instrument, encompassing five key dimensions to realize the role of the educational objectives of Islamic worship among university students.

In light of the study's findings, a proposed framework was developed to enhance the role of these educational objectives in enabling university youth to confront the problems associated with modern technology.

Keywords: Educational Objectives of Worship – Technology Challenges -university youth.

Introduction:

Modern technological communication tools play a central role in enhancing human interaction and facilitating the rapid transmission of information and knowledge. These tools have contributed to reducing distances between youth, individuals, and communities, creating greater opportunities for collaboration and cultural and economic exchange. In addition, modern technology provides innovative educational tools and new job opportunities, while also contributing to the spread of awareness and social and political development. However, these tools require balanced use to ensure the preservation of cultural identity and societal values.

It is essential to emphasize that modern technology plays a significant role in society, with its scope extending worldwide from east to west. However, it is considered a double-edged sword, as it can have both positive and negative effects on individuals and society alike. On the positive side, modern technology can contribute to the development of knowledge and education, and it can help enhance social communication. Additionally, it can play a role in improving healthcare and medical services. However, modern technology can also have a negative impact on society, and excessive reliance on technology may lead to social isolation and a disconnect between individuals. Furthermore, technology can contribute to the spread of fake news and inaccurate information (Al-Hassan & Mohammed, 2019, pp. 412-418).

In addition to the above, the world today is witnessing rapid and profound changes in the fields of communication and modern technology. The impact of these changes extends to the system of cultural values, and within this reality, new values associated with globalization emerge. The choice that Arabs must make is to address these circumstances with seriousness and realism. When dealing with the implications of globalization, we must be aware of the cultural

effects that arise from it, while at the same time, we must preserve our cultural identity, religious values, and civilizational heritage. This can be achieved through the adoption of a selective approach that chooses what aligns with our values, beliefs, and religion, while avoiding what contradicts them (Abu Khunjar, 2015, p. 347).

Since the four acts of worship in Islam — prayer, zakat, fasting, and pilgrimage — hold a significant place, they are considered pillars of this great religion. 1 .As the Messenger of Allah, peace be upon him, said: "Islam is built upon five [pillars]: the testimony that there is no god but Allah, and that Muhammad is His servant and messenger, the establishment of prayer, the giving of zakat, the pilgrimage to the House [Kaaba], and fasting during the month of Ramadan" (Bukhari, 2002, Vol. 2, p. 12, Hadith 8). The educational objective of these acts of worship is to elevate the human soul, purify it, achieve a state of psychological tranquility, and correct improper behaviors.

It is important to emphasize that strengthening faith and religious education are among the legitimate objectives in the upbringing of adolescents, as they are vital aspects of their development. This can be achieved through a variety of educational methods and practices based on academic principles and an educational perspective. These points are derived from Islamic law and translated into educational terms through the enhancement of faith and religious upbringing. This can be accomplished by teaching the Quran and the Sunnah of the Prophet, with a focus on promoting mercy and honoring parents, which is considered one of the most important Islamic duties. This can be achieved through fostering emotional connection and effective communication between adolescents and their parents. Additionally, preserving chastity and combating immoral behaviors should guide youth to avoid negative behaviors and vices (Bin Humaid, 2018, p. 8).

The Holy Quran is considered an important spiritual source that influences and nurtures the human soul. Many experts in the field of psychological therapy agree that faith plays a crucial role in achieving inner peace and psychological healing. Faith in Allah enhances mental health and provides tranquility and stability to the soul. When this faith

is instilled at an early age, it offers psychological immunity and a sense of security and peace (Shukr, 2018, p. 23).

It is worth noting that Islamic acts of worship bear various spiritual fruits. Just as fasting leads to the purification of the soul, zakat purifies wealth, and pilgrimage focuses on the duty of forgiveness, the fruit of prayer is manifested in turning towards Allah. Prayer, which is one of the most important spiritual pillars in Islam, allows the youth to demonstrate their sincerity and devotion in worship and closeness to Allah. The importance of turning to Allah is evident in all aspects of worship, as this devotion reflects a deep connection with the spiritual aspects of the individual (Al-Zarqi, 2009, p. 51).

Therefore, acts of worship occupy a central place in the daily life of youth. They are not merely religious rituals, but rather means to deepen faith and strengthen the relationship with Allah. A Muslim's daily life begins with prayer, which organizes their time and reminds them of their responsibilities towards their Creator. Fasting, for example, is not only a means to achieve piety but also helps in disciplining the soul and abstaining from desires. Zakat is a means of purifying wealth and the soul, while promoting social solidarity. Hajj is a great act of worship that manifests the perfection of monotheism and submission to Allah, purifying the soul from sins and transgressions. Acts of worship in a Muslim's day enhance their discipline and make them mindful of their actions and words, which reflects in their behavior and interactions with others. In general, worship in the daily life of a Muslim forms an ethical and spiritual framework that supports them in their quest to balance the demands of this world and the duties of the Hereafter.

Problem of the Study and Its Questions:

Excessive use of modern technology leads individuals to acquire undesirable behaviors, such as reduced ability to focus on studies, weakened social relationships, and moral corruption. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that technology plays an important role in shaping individuals' behavior and lifestyle (Hindi & Al-Rifai, 2017, p. 2).

The problem of the study lies in addressing the issues resulting from university youth's use of modern technological tools. The greatest challenge faced by youth in the era of globalization is the impact of satellite TV and modern technological media on their values and beliefs. Youth are the group most exposed to rapid changes and influenced by them due to their orientation toward the future and their desire to explore what is new and innovative (Sayed, 2008, p. 162).

Therefore, the topic of the research was chosen to focus on the role of the educational purposes of Islamic acts of worship in addressing the challenges of modern technology among university youth. The emphasis is placed on the educational objectives of these acts of worship because they continuously renew the Muslim individual's spirit, providing them with light, strength, emotion, hope, and repentance that purifies the heart. Additionally, the practice of worship protects youth from indulging in a world of desires, serving as a support in confronting the problems posed by modern technology and the difficulties of life.

Based on the above, the problem of the study is crystallized in the following main question:

- What is the role of the educational objectives of Islamic acts of worship in addressing the challenges of modern technology among university youth?

From this main question, a set of sub-questions arises as follows:

1. What is meant by modern technological communication tools? What are the problems and benefits resulting from their use among university youth?
2. What is the concept of the educational objectives of Islamic acts of worship? What are the most important educational objectives of these acts of worship?
3. How does the practice of worship help youth in addressing the issues related to modern technological communication tools?
4. How can we benefit from the educational effects of Islamic acts of worship in improving the behaviors of university youth? And how can we lead youth to achieve psychological tranquility?

Objectives of the Study:

1. To monitor modern technological communication tools and identify the problems and benefits resulting from their use.
2. To define the concept of the educational objectives of Islamic acts of worship and clarify the most important educational objectives of these acts of worship.
3. To demonstrate the impact of youth's practice of Islamic acts of worship on addressing the challenges of using modern technological communication tools.
4. To explore how to benefit from the educational effects of worship in improving the behaviors of university youth.
5. To understand how to lead youth to achieve psychological tranquility and protect them from mental and physical health issues.

Importance of the Study:

The Islamic approach links the individual to a noble and high goal, making the purpose of their life the worship of Allah alone. Islam helps individuals and communities align in their daily lives, while also working on building and developing the young person's character by encouraging them to take responsibility for self-monitoring. Islam offers individuals various self-healing methods, such as worship, seeking forgiveness, repentance, patience, and remembrance (dhikr), which assist the individual in restoring their psychological balance in all the situations they face in life through worship. Through worship, an individual can connect with Allah, feel spiritual comfort, and experience closeness to Him (Al-Saleem, 2016, pp. 411-412).

The educational objectives of Islamic acts of worship are considered one of the fundamental pillars in developing ethical and behavioral awareness among university youth, especially in light of the increasing challenges posed by modern technology. These objectives contribute to the refinement of the soul, the enhancement of human conscience, and the development of self-monitoring, which limits the tendency to engage in the negative use of technology, such as digital addiction or social isolation. Therefore, employing the educational objectives of

worship represents an effective tool in preparing a generation of university youth capable of positively interacting with the realities of the modern age without compromising core values.

Research Methodology and Tools:

The researcher used the descriptive method, which is defined as an attempt to reach accurate and detailed knowledge about the elements of a specific problem or phenomenon. This process involves collecting facts, information, and observations related to these elements or phenomena in order to achieve a better and more precise understanding. This approach is employed to establish future policies and procedures related to these elements or phenomena, based on reliable knowledge and available academic research (Al-Mahmoudi, 2019, p. 46).

This study relied on a questionnaire as a tool for collecting data from students at Al-Arish University.

Study Terminology:

Operational Definition of the Educational Objectives of Islamic Acts of Worship:

These are the educational foundations derived from acts of worship, which form the basis of the human education system in building experiences. This leads to the holistic and comprehensive development of the individual's personality, directing their behaviors, and regulating their morals according to the authentic Islamic educational approach. Through this, youth can be guided to reach psychological and physical tranquility and self-discipline in all their behaviors.

Operational Definition of Worship:

This religious term refers to the specific actions and deeds performed by an individual as an expression of their connection to Allah or higher spiritual powers. Worship is one of the fundamental aspects of religious life in various religions. It encompasses a wide range of acts and rituals performed by individuals and communities within the

framework of their religious beliefs and teachings, aimed at seeking the pleasure of Allah.

Operational Definition of Modern Technological Communication Tools:
This can be operationally defined as the means and technologies that enable individuals to communicate and interact with each other over distances using modern electronic and digital technologies.

Operational Definition of the Problems of Modern Technology:

These are the challenges and issues that arise due to the rapid advancement of new technologies. These problems are multidimensional, covering various aspects related to society, economy, ethics, security, and the environment.

Previous Studies:

A) Study by Abu Hamidi (2011) titled: "The Educational Objectives of the Prophetic Biography"

The study aimed to enlighten those studying Islamic education about the characteristics of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) and how to benefit from them in the contemporary and future reality of the Muslim community. It also aimed to establish educational foundations for generations based on the prophetic biography, to educate and purify the individuals of the Muslim community through the life of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), and to achieve leadership for the Muslim nation by educating community members on the path the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) followed to reach safety. The researcher used the descriptive, analytical, and deductive method, where the educational objectives were extracted from the prophetic biography. The study concluded with several key findings: describing the life of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) as easy and straightforward, considering individual differences among people, and the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) adopting a preventive and therapeutic approach to solve many people's problems. The life and biography of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) are based on principles of education and purification for the generation of the companions through applying the rules of the Qur'an in their lives. The prophetic biography aids in understanding the Book

of Allah and how to implement its rulings, and it is a tangible representation of the principles and rulings of Islam.

B) Study by Bloul and Barika (2016) titled: "The Impact of Using Social Media Networks as a Communication and Media Tool on University Students: A Field Study on a Sample of University Students at Abu Al-Qasim Saadallah University"

The study aimed to identify the impact of internet sites (social media networks) on the values of university students, as well as to monitor, evaluate, and analyze the relationship of youth with modern media at the present time by determining the frequency of internet use, and identifying the most influential and contributing platforms in changing social values. The researchers used the descriptive method, and the study concluded with the following key findings: The study revealed that 42% of university students use social media networks daily, making the internet a significant source from which university youth acquire their culture. It also showed that Facebook ranked first among social media platforms that university youth engage with, with a high percentage of 75.5%. The study further indicated that the internet was most commonly used for recreational and personal needs, as university students seek to satisfy a range of social and psychological needs. Finally, the study clarified the negative effects of internet use on students and its role in changing some social values.

C) Study by Abd al-Qader (2016) titled: "Manifestations of Mental Health in the Qur'an"

The study aimed to define the concept of mental health, explore the factors affecting it, and identify some of the manifestations of mental health in the Qur'an. The researcher used the inductive research method, which involves extensive reading on the subject, reviewing scientific sources and literature, and analyzing the opinions, trends, and ideas that led to specific conclusions. The study concluded that the Qur'an addresses the soul through several methods that enable an individual to enjoy mental well-being. These methods include: instilling faith in the belief of monotheism in the soul, planting the seeds of piety in the heart, which leads to significant outcomes in shaping personality and behavior; prescribing various acts of worship that help abandon

many bad habits and adopt good ones, thereby aiding in the development of a balanced and wholesome personality; encouraging regular remembrance of God, which creates a sense of closeness to God, His protection, and care, filling the individual with a sense of security and peace; and urging forgiveness and repentance, which helps relieve anxiety caused by feelings of guilt.

D) Study (Fahd, 2020) titled: "The Educational Purposes of Cosmic Verses and the Scientific Miracles of the Qur'an"

The study aimed to clarify the concept of the cosmic verses, their purpose, and the most important educational objectives and purposes for which they were revealed. It emphasized the necessity of reflecting on and contemplating the cosmic verses, as well as the guidelines for their scientific interpretation. Additionally, the study explored the earthly verses and the important phenomena that Allah Almighty has made available to make the earth suitable for life. The researcher employed an inductive and analytical approach, examining the Qur'anic verses that reveal the educational purposes of the cosmic verses, analyzing the relationship between the meaning of each purpose and the scientific miracles of the Qur'an, and then drawing conclusions. The study concluded with the following key findings: proving the existence of the Creator, His oneness, His greatness, management, and wisdom. Reflecting on the marvelous works of the Creator has a significant impact on strengthening faith and enhancing the connection with Allah. It also encourages the pursuit of knowledge and its expansion in all fields, not limiting oneself to just one area, as this contributes to the improvement of human life. Undoubtedly, the Qur'an is Allah's eternal miracle, which He has preserved from distortion, as He says in the Qur'an: "Indeed, We have sent down the Qur'an, and indeed, We will be its guardian" (Al-Hijr: 9).

E) The study by Al-Muslih (2021) titled "The Five Purposes of Creation and the Essence of True Education (A Study in Light of the Qur'an)"

The study aimed to examine the five purposes of creation: worship, vicegerency on Earth, its development, testing, and the diversity

among people. It also sought to analyze the relationships among these five purposes and their connection to the essence of true education, which is the noble ascent towards the heights of perfection. This was based on the researcher's analysis of the concept of true education in a previous semantic foundational study. The research was conducted using a foundational analytical methodology in light of the Qur'an. This involved extrapolating the verses that reveal the purposes of creation, studying them semantically, and comparing them within their contexts. The relationship between the meaning of each purpose and the essence of true education was analyzed, and the key results and their implications were drawn. The study concluded with the following key findings: The most significant revelation of the research is that, to the extent to which a person embodies the requirements of the five purposes of creation, as indicated by their meanings in light of the Qur'an, they fulfill their humanity and ascend to the highest levels of human perfection, bringing them closer to their Lord, the ultimate model of perfection. This ascent is the essence of true education. True education, in its essence, has the potential to elevate the human being comprehensively toward infinite perfection, which encompasses the purposes of creation. This comprehensive ascent reshapes the individual in all aspects, as if they were a newly created being.

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